

Kur River Valley Sassanian and Islamic Pottery:
Justification for the Chronological Classification of Sites

Period S. (ca. < 800 A.D.)

Type pottery: unglazed, burnished, and slipped {wares} with distinctive profiles.
Type sites: mounds above Naqsh-i-Rustam {and} Qasr-i-Abu Nasr spoil heap.
Dating: Pas{agardae} Takt IV {IV? throughout} has no associated glazed pottery. {These types of} Pottery {are} found in abundance at Qasr-i-Abu Nasr in early Islamic and late Sassanian context (1).
Terminal date: exceedingly rare on the surface of Istakhr and in Schmidt's trenches, which have abundant very early polychrome glazed ware {that was} introduced c.a. 800 A.D.

Period 1. (ca. 800-1150 A.D.)

Type pottery: splashed ware (c.f. Sirjan kiln ware), thin yellow glaze, spinach green (c.f. Nishapur).
Type sites: Istakhr and Field Number 648 {problem, 648 is not on Andrew's list of classified sites}, both of which have a wide range of polychrome glazed ware and practically no 'Seljuc' frit ware, which became very common after ca. 1150 A.D. This is probably the most discrete period since its beginning and end are determined by important technological innovations. It is also best represented at Siraf.

Period 2. (ca. 1150-1500 A.D.)

Type pottery: 'Seljuc' frit body, lustre on frit body, Chekiang celadon, flange and hammer rims on body (c.f. Siraf IV).
Dating: The earliest frit body is c.a. 1150 A.D. (the earliest piece with a painted date is 1179 A.D.). A large number of painted dates on lustre are from 1179-1339 A.D.
Chekiang celadon {was} introduced {in} Siraf IV. {Parallels for pottery of this period are found in 15th century A.D. material from Siraf IV, the pots set in the roof of 'The house of the Mosque' at Kilwa (east Africa) (2), and {found in} the upper levels of the Takht {at Pasargadae}. (3) However a mihrab from Abarquh in the Shiraz museum carries the date 809 A.H. (1406 A.D.) under a very glassy glaze. (4) Its condition could be the result of not being buried or it might not be as old as the painted date indicates. The pattern and style of decoration are unlike any of the potter listed above {for this period}. I am studying the problem. This period could be subdivided into two at about 1350 A.D., that is before the introduction of Siraf IV pottery or Chekiang celadon.

Period 3. (c.a. 1500-)

Type pottery: late Persian blue and white from Kerman etc., glossy surfaced turquoise glazed ware, Japanese export porcelain.
Dating: {types of} pottery absent from Siraf IV, but present in small later deposits at Siraf, {Site G.} Painted dates on late blue and white {fall within the} 16-18th centuries A.D.
Japanese export porcelain {dates} from the 19th century A.D. onwards.

Because of the lack of stratigraphically excavated sites in the area this whole framework, and especially the later periods, must be treated with caution.

Andrew Williamson
1969

Additional Pottery notes

Don, here is a sorted list of sites that were classified by Andrew as shown in columns for Islamic Periods 3, 2, 1, and Sasanian. The descriptions in the comments column are from my field notes with just one or two quotes from Andrew for sites with a W- field number, which he surveyed, and several notes from Alden for sites with an A- field number either in column B or the comments column. So, it is my hope these descriptions may help sort out the chronological markers he used. The following abbreviations are used in the comments column: gl=glaze, h=hard ware, meaning hard fired, usually with grit temper, a utilitarian plain ware; sy= soft yellow ware, sl=slip, brn=burnished, mm=mold made relief decorated ware, r=red, g=grey, Mad=Madabad wares--it is clear that I recognized at least 3 varieties. I have not yet found the notes in which I explain the numbers used to distinguish them. The same problem with the letter abbreviations in () such as "(tpcis)" or "(mpis)" which I know were used to describe attributes such as slip or paste or temper. I may have given the only copy to Andrew! The conventions or grammar used in the notes is: h-r&g = red and grey hard wares; sl-r = red slipped ware; for "u/" read under as in "black u/t" = black paint under turquoise glaze (this is surely not a correct technical description, it is just how it looked to me); for "/" read "on" as in red sl/buff = red slip on buff ware or r/g = red paint on grey surface (these are simple 'It looks like' descriptions and don't pretend to be technically correct at all); for "w/" read "with" as in "w/ tab handle". Where the comments column refers to "Islamic" it means I classified the assemblage as Islamic in the field or before I turned the collection over to Andrew. Give me a call or an email with questions. I have not completed the editing of this list but I doubt if any corrections I make will change the character of the information, if indeed there is any information here. I assume you still have a copy of Andrews one page typed "Kur River Valley Sassanian and Islamic Pottery: Justification for the Chronological Classification of Sites." If not, let me know. This list is only that part of the site inventory with Andrew's classification. There are an additional 400+ sites classified as Islamic on morphological (K=kharabi or S= stone walls or tent stands= Islamic, or Q = qale, often =Sasanian) or simply on the basis of my summary conviction that the pottery is "Islamic" or "Sasanian"

NOTES:

Field number 106 1) red "rolling board w/ one leg 2) sherd with turquoise glaze and red paint on unglazed part of base 3) black painted design under turquoise glaze 4) flange rim red and grey plain hard wares

115 1) red and grey hard wares 2) slipped wares 3) miscl plain wares

318 1) good selection of glazed sherds 2) hard (ict) ware 3) soft yellow ware (msict) 4) red-brown/buff 5) dark grey/grey 6) nipple lugs 7) rubbed (I think the same as wiped slip)

321 1) glaze 2) hard ware (cs) 3) soft yellow /w twisted handle (ms) 4) grey slipped ware 5) brown or grey paint on buff ware

322 1) procelain 2) black painted design under blue glaze 3)red and grey hard fired plain wares 4) soft yellow ware (mi) 5) glass

335 1) dark slip on hard red ware 2) purple-brown paint on buff ware

357 1) soft yellow ware 2) red and grey slipped wares 3) brown bands on buff ware 4) grey ribbed ware 5) miscl coarse wares 6) glass

369 1) black on blue under glaze, tang splash 2) hard wares 3) punctate and incised buff rim 4) orange and brown slipped wares 5) "green" paint ?? on light buff rim 6) Madabad polished brown ware including a loop handle (plain and incised) 7) glass 8) heavy pottery legs 9) medium fine plain grey ware

370 1) glaze: black, white & blue; black & blue; turquoise; flange rim 2) Madabad 3) hard red & grey 3) moulded 4) miscl slip 5) glass

371 1) green glaze 2) hard grey 3) unusual "nail impressed" w/red polish 4) madabad painted and polished 5) miscl slips 6) good selection of glass

372 1) hard red & grey 2) glaze, flange rim 3) soft yellow 4) grey/ buff slip rim 5) untypical Madabad polished brown rim

375 Madabad type site. 1) brown on yellow-buff 2) brown to red polished semiflange rim w/ vertical striations, sometimes w/incised decor and strap handle (draw)

384 1) glaze: turquoise, blue & white, black w/ blue & white 2) hard red & grey 3) moulded

391 Mostly Islamic standard, some red/buff; kiln on this site. 1) hard red (spout) & grey 2) hard red w/ grey slip 3) flange rim 4) polished red slip 5) small bricks 6) brown/buff flower pot ware 7) painted flower pot

393 1) glaze: black under blue; black/blue/white 2) hard wares 3) grey/buff slip 4) moulded ware 5) plain buff 6) one sherd Mad brown/buff? 7) bricks 215x210x45 mm

396 1) wasters, firing tripods 2) hard red punctate 3) white and brown moulded 4) black under blue glaze 5) Tang splash? 6) white relief on grey? slip under clear glaze? 7) heavy red on red slip

397 1) Glaze: turquoise; tang splash, flange rim 2) miscl plain wares 3) variation on Madabad semi-flange? 4) miscl heavy slipped wares 5) firing tripods, firing rings, firedogs (drawings)

502B 1) glaze: Black U/ turquoise, relief decoration, flange rim 2) Madabad 3) nebulous polished slipped red 4) miscl plain w/ grey slip 5) 1 sherd white, brown, buff 6) decorated and plain soft ware incl loop handle? 7) glass bangles 8) carinated stone bowl

505 1) glaze: porcelain and celadon 2) hard grey 3) plain buff 4) unusual hard grey with maroon slip (new comment Late Banesh?, not likely)

513 1) glaze: turquoise, sgraffito under yellow, tang splash 2) painted flower pots, 3) one sherd black bands/coarse heavy red ware 4) unusual grey slip base (drawing) 5) moulded and stamped yellow wares

519 1) glaze: tang splash, black u/ blue, flange rim, fine profile 2) madabad wares 3) painted flower pots 4) red flat base (like Lapui ware?) 5) miscl plain & slipped 6) hard red and grey, 7) fragment of lug of foot 8) lug handle on plain buff (drawing)

521 Glaze: porcelain, white & grey, black u/ turquoise 2) plain grey (Achaemenid??) 3) polished red slipped flat base bowl 4) 1 sherd Madabad painted 5) Bakun sherd 6) glass

523 1) glaze: porcelain ?, turquoise, tang splash ? variety of prehistoric and unidentified wares

531 1) glazed lamp, blue glaze ornaments? 2) nail impressed cream ware 3) Madabad painted, 1 sherd 4) painted flowerpot? 5) miscl grey and dark brown-red slip, one with lug? or annular rib

550 mound against talus, platform on mound w/ moat on 3 sides away from talus, stone tent stands on mound outside platform. 1) "trifurcate handle" in reddish buff (quoting Andrew?) 2) miscl plain Islamic, 3) glaze, glass, mould made 4) sherd of soft ware stone? bottle or pipe neck (drawing)

562 1) tang splash?, incised under lemon yellow 2) hard red 3) grey paint/ buff 4) ribbed ware some w/ purple slip 5) grey slip 6) red slip inside/buff 7) glass, flint, iron, stone bowl

5702 combined 570 and 572 570 = 1) Islamic hard wares 2) glaze 3) stamped 4) Madabad 2 5) wiped slip 572 = 1) Islamic hard wares 2) glaze 3) madabad 2, 3 4) celadon 5) polished red slip (Kaftari) 6) glass

5B7 4 sherds: grey slipped everted hole-mouth jar rim, heavy grey rim, ribbed grey rim, polished brown rim

5S3&5 Very extensive group of small mounds, 2 oil press stones, column base (drawing), Emamzadeh, Madabad ware

5T9 fortress ? town ruins, no standing wall stubs, retaining wall, qale mound lower down. no glaze seen, Lapui or Lapui-like red wares, "later plain wares", 1 sherd Mad

607 1) glaze: porcelain & green drip from rim over rosy buff 2) polished red sherd 3) brown/creamy slip 4) miscl plain wares 5) glass bottle neck

638 1) glaze 2) mould made, 3) hard red & grey 4) miscl plain: buff, red & grey 5) Madabad ware 6) glass

639 1) glaze: black/ turquoise, black/white slip w/ blue in clear glaze 2) polished red slip (KAF) 3) Madabad 4) brown/pinkish buff 5) black/white slip band (Late Banesh??) 6) miscl plain

GRID	FIELD #	3	2	1	S	COMMENT
56898873	S-206	1				gl, h, sy, coarse sl buff, wiped slip
56899806	S-204				1	gl, sl, heavy g, plain wares, painted ?, many flints
57886765	S-200		1		1	gl-blue; standing stone and mud brk walls
57898823	S-103	1				ruins of hamum on naturall hill
57899413	S-104		1			poss burial (femur)
57900725	S-207				1	
57902925	S-231	1				h (p b), sl, grey rib, pierced lug, tab handle
57917049	S-418	1				Islamic
58859572	S-562				1	NOTE
58878780	S-127	1			1	gl, h, sy, red/buff crows foot
58881091	S-105		1			gl, h, sy, sl
58882877	S-102	1				recent K on earlier site, hamum in use 25 yrs ago
58883448	S-116	1				gl, h, heavy yellow w/ deep scratches, stone walls vis
58883892	S-332		1			gl- black under t; black, white, blue; t
58883927	S-119	1				h-r & g, sl-r & g, brown/buff paint?
58884756	S-117				1	
58885043	S-118	1				no sherd description, scatter along talus
58885190	S-330	1			1	gl, h (i), sy (s)
58886508	S-122	1	1			series of excellent caves
58886537	S-113		1		1	white mound, bed rock mortars
58886875	S-306	1				gl, h (c s), sy, heavy grey
58887622	S-100	1				no sherd description, fort on prom, edge of valley
58888122	S-112	1				gl, sy, sl-g & r, grey banded sl, painted rim?
58888748	S-304	1				gl-t, h-r&g, mm, tubular spout
58888841	S-114	1				no sherd description, on river bank
58889829	S-302	1				no sherd description, burials
58890461	S-106	1	1			gl-t, h-g&r, sl-g; note 1
58896274	S-336	1	1			gl, h (cpt), sy (mcs)
58898675	S-339	1				no sherd description
58899512	S-319	1	1			selection of gl, h (tpcis), sy (mpis), glass
59865536	S-558	1	1			gl-black u/t, Islamic hard wares
59866628	S-559	1			1	gl, grey paint/grey, brown-red sl, mm, stamped
59867422	S-560	1				sl-brownish & r, grey sherds
59871896	S-108	1				ploughed down
59874447	S-130	1				no sherd description
59874857	S-129		1		1	gl, h-r&g, sy, slip?; talus, swr
59880110	S-109	1				50 yr old ruined hamum nearby
59880125	S-301	1				gl, h, sy; bones
59881077	S-324	1	1			gl, h (p), sy (pmis), brown/buff
59881585	S-318	1				NOTE
59882776	V-316				1	gl, h, sy,(m s), sl-r&g, glass. J-11K2
59883415	S	1	1		1	KUH-I ISTAKHR
59884458	S-313		1		1	
59885845	S-312	1			1	gl, sy (m i), sl-g, glass
59887290	S-358	1				gl-lamp, h, sy, hard fine thin grey, glass
59897604	S-357				1	NOTE

GRID	FIELD #	3	2	1	S	COMMENT
59915215	S	1	1			I assigned period 2, 3; don't know how.
60846479	S-566			1		gl, rough g, red, Islamic
60846778	S-567		1	1		gl, plain g, painted, bangles
60847007	S-5X2				1	plain wares
60848164	S-5K0				1	iridescent glass, crude plain & dark burn slip
60849793	S-5W9	1				1 Islamic sherd, several unident
60850555	S-563	1	1			notes say no sherds found??
60851553	S-564	1	1			Islamic. A-101-I
60851949	S-564C	1				description only of prehistoric sherds
60862485	S-500		1			A-101-I, kiln
60862589	S-501		1			
60871376	S-308	1	1			no mention of Islamic sherds in my notes
60871485	V-367		1	1		
60871550	S-3A5		1			Mad, flange rim, other possible Islamic
60872898	S-390	1				gl-black under blue, h-r&g, Mad painted?
60873169	S-370		1			NOTE
60873677	S-369		1	1	1	NOTE
60873801	S-526	1				gl-t, sl-brown
60873807	S-5Q9			1	1	gl, sl
60874551	S-321	1	1	1		NOTE
60875345	S-372		1			NOTE
60876594	S-384	1	1			NOTE
60878266	S-375		1	1		NOTE; MADABAD type site
60878436	S-633	1				glazed bowl, Mad, flange rim
60878764	S-374		1			gl-t, Mad, miscl plain & slipped, mm
60879493	S-392	1	1	1		gl, h, mm, Mad, miscl plain, alabaster
60879584	S-393	1	1			NOTE
60879770	S-373	1				gl-blue, h (spouts), plain buff, incised, sl-r rim (draw)
60880100	S-366		1			gl-blue&lustre, h, coarse, fine buff, Mad a&b, tile
60883169	S-376B			1	1	gl-tang? & blue, h-g, mm, Mad painted, sl-g
60883736	S-365	1	1			gl-light blue, black u/ t; mm; h-r&g
60884112	S-371	1	1	1		NOTE
60884112	S-391	1	1	1	1	NOTE, kiln, tumulus
60885676	S-399	1	1			gl-t, mm, h-r&g, Mad, unique carved grey sherd
60886685	S-345		1			gl, sy, madabad (semi-flange), sl-g,
60888933	S-397		1	1		NOTE, kiln
60888954	S-398	1	1			gl-t, miscl plain & sl, painted flower pot
60893220	S-352		1	1		gl, h-r, sy (mic), sl-g, black paint/coarse grey
61835613	R-SAS77				1	
61836841	S-5S1		1		1	Mad, plain, old Baiza?
61838761	S				1	"Peter Parthian/Selucid", stone bust, burials
61839160	S-5S0	1				Islamic (A-9F3-I, 3 Islamic sherds)
61839833	S-5X8	1				kiln, coin, some Islamic sherds
61839851	S-5X6	1				1 Islamic & unident late plain wares
61851132	S-5N7	1	1			Islamic, Mad
61852295	S-531	1			1	NOTE

GRID	FIELD #	3	2	1	S	COMMENT
61857006	S-5H0	1				Islamic, gl, grey lug
61863007	S-536	1				Gl-tang splash, Mad, yellow mm, plain
61864077	S-674	1				porcelain, flange rim
61864824	S-504	1				gl-porcelain (modern?), Mad, h-r&buff, sl, glass
61865104	V-5E1		1	1		Mad painted, misck Islamic; HOSAINABAD
61865408	S-5E2	1	1			gl, Mad, flower pot, r tab handle, polished r
61865739	S-505		1			NOTE
61866527	V-537	1			1	gl-blue, coarse painted ware, miscl plain wares
61867850	S-5B1	1				various prehistoric, Mad painted ?
61868210	S-514			1	1	gl, Mad (flower pot), buff w/ rim lug, sl, glass
61868245	S-5B4			1		polished red sl, glass bangle
61868527	S-5D0		1			gl, Mad painted, flower pot, polish; mm, soft ware
61868759	V-5B0				1	plain wares
61868759	V-5B0				1	
61868805	S-502B	1	1			NOTE
61871362	S-660	1				stone column 37 cm dia, stone bowl
61872591	S-607	1			1	NOTE
61875425	S-669		1			Mad
61875738	S-668	1	1			Mad
61877166	S-644	1	1	1		porcelain, Mad, bangles, storage jar. J-9J3-I
61877365	V-6423	1				Islamic. J-643
61879138	S-684	1				
61880319	S-394	1				gl, h-r&g, mm, mad painted
61883403	S-657	1	1			fine porcelain, bricks
61887295	V-629				1	
61888244				1	1	
61888301	S-634	1	1			Mad, Islamic
61888615	V-638		1			NOTE
62821695	S-5V5	1				porcelain, glass
62826196	S-5V0				1	heavy coarse plain ware
62830694	S-5Y6			1		Mad, unident sherds
62831259	S-5R8	1			1	Malyan, Islamic=NE corner, Sas=SW quadrant
62831333	S-BZA				1	
62838044	S-5U1	1				Mad, black/red?
62838786	S-5S6				1	
62842165	S-5L9	1				unident, dark red/red-orange, plain; A-8G2-I
62843087	S-5K8	1	1			gl, Mad
62843096	S-5J9			1		gl, g lug hndl, wiped paint
62844783	S-5J2	1		1	1	gl-luster, Mad paint, plain g, white bnd/r-brn sl
62846818	S-5T8			1		
62847926	S-5T9		1		1	NOTE
62848873	S-554	1				gl-porcelain, green lamp, scratched soft, painted?
62850715	S-5N4	1				gl-porcelain, blue; heavy grey
62853764	S-523	1		1		NOTE
62856047	S-519		1	1		NOTE
62857086	S-543	1				coin, gl-porcelain, unident paint & incis soft ware

GRID	FIELD #	3	2	1	S	COMMENT
62857744	S-569	1				scruffy late plain wares
62859212	S-550	1				NOTE
62860563	S-5B7				1	NOTE
62860701	S-507		1			gl-t, black u/t; h-r&g, mm, Mad painted?, bangles
62861257	S-5C0			1		tang splash, Mad?, mm, sl-g, buff, glass
62861366	S-5B8	1				gl, black/red festoons, r/r bands, sl-g, flat bases
62861569	S-5B9			1		g/buff Mad, sl-r, mm, plain buff
62862155	S-5C1	1	1			sl-r polished, Mad 2, greybrown/buff, plain
62862233	S-BAZ				1	
62862328	S-513			1		NOTE
62864750	S-681	1				plain wares
62866411	S-544	1				gl-turquoise
62867061	S-213	1	1	1	1	gl, h (c p) sy, sl-r, spout
62869243	S-678			1		gl-green, Mad, moulded duck
62870178	S-616			1		Mad, mm "lion" motif, standard Islamic
62872897	S-641			1		gl- brown & green, mm, plain
62875133	S-676	1				qale mound made of prehitiric mound?
62881203	S-639		1			NOTE
63824543	R-				1	MZC230
63830269	S-5S3-5	1	1			NOTE
63841224	S-557	1	1			gl-t, flange rim; Islamic plain. A-7G7-I
63842999	S-595	1		1		gl, sl-r&g, 2 painted
63843996	S-597	1				Islamic polished red, black/red?
63847740	NE				1	
63850023	S-521	1				NOTE, A-8G1-I, column base
63850237	S-546				1	scruffy plain & slipped, alabaster frag
63850244	S-5702	1				NOTE
63850646	S-571	1	1			only prehistoric sherds described
63850952	S-573			1		moulded green glaze, grey slip
63851169	S-574	1				gl-deep blue, green, porc.; plain spout, Mad 1
63851239	S-547			1		plain & slipped, shell, quern
63852247	S-548	1				h-g, glass; Islamic
63853041	S-549	1	1			gl-black u/ t, h-r, incised soft ware, painted ?
63853422	S-593	1	1	1		gl-flange rim, Mad 1, 2, 3; heavy g, heavy foot
63854261	S-590	1		1		gl, Mad 3, plain Islamic
63854665	S-588			1		Madabad, polished red slipped foot
63854976	S-691			1		coarse grey and red wares, ribbed ware
63855352	S-591	1				gl-green, plain, poss Sasanian
64823194	W-7M4	1				Islamic
64823494	W-7M3		1	1		Islamic 1 & 2
64824294	W-7M2	1				sporatic Islamic
64832545	S-738		1			Islamic
64835002	W-7M9	1				Islamic 3
64836878	S-713			1		plain wares (2 drawings)
65820148	S-722			1		k on tall steep Islamic mound on river bank
66856627	S-817		1	1		gl-tang splash & t, half moon lug /grey, glass

GRID	FIELD #	3	2	1	S	COMMENT
66856633	S-816	1	1			notes only mention prehistoric wares
67835289	S-813			1		
67838668	S-819		1	1		gl-green&t, Mad,
67842384	S-8X2			1		
67847702	S-818				1	red, grey, & buff wares, ribbed ware
67851000	S-8X1	1				
68820176	S-821				1	
68835686	S-803		1	1		Islamic w/ Mad, glass
68836297	S-810		1	1		gl-t, green, blue, flange rim, excellent flint
68838852	S-807			1		Islamic w/ tang splash?, Mad
69812497	S-827			1		Mad, plain wares
69813178	S-828				1	smoky grey & white coarse, red w/legs, no gl
69821778	S-806				1	gl-t, Mad, glass, tab handle (drawing)
69831525	S-804			1	1	gl-green & violet, heavy ware w/ thumb imp/relief
	S-209			1	1	gl, sl-r&g, sy, r sl leg, brwn/y buff, blk/red
	S-210				1	sl-r, heavy incised buff
	S-212		1	1		gl-blue grey, h (c p), s-y, sl-r&g, loop handle, glass
	S-214		1		1	
	S-215		1	1		gl, h-r&g, sy, sl, glass
	S-217				1	sl-r, wiped slip, brown&r/buff sl
	S-218				1	gl, h?, red/buff slip; ploughed down
	S-219	1				gl, sy (c), gl w/r/buff
	S-220				1	gl, h (p c) sy (msi), glass